

Discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing policies in Laos: Implications for greenhouse gas emissions and food security

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ABSTRACT

Land-use competition between forest conservation and agricultural food production poses major threats to climate change mitigation and food security. Land sparing policies aim at reconciling this conundrum by intensifying agriculture while conserving forests, but scientific debates prevail about their effectiveness. To contribute to this debate, we analyze the discursive dimension of land sparing efforts and their biophysical implications for Lao PDR. Applying an interdisciplinary mixed-methods approach, we examine how Lao land-use policies legitimize land sparing at the cost of shifting cultivation and how land use changed between 2000 and 2019. We quantify ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions and investigate trends in agricultural production and food security. We find that policy documents use both socio-economic and environmental arguments to substantiate land sparing at the expense of shifting cultivation. In biophysical terms, the stabilization of shifting cultivation enhanced the recovery of some forest areas resulting in gross carbon sequestration while ecosystems in total remained a net source of emissions. Concomitant agricultural intensification improved dietary energy supply, reduced the prevalence of undernourishment, and increased agricultural exports. However, cropland expansion and the intensification of agriculture entailed greenhouse gas emissions of similar extent as the continuing shifting cultivation, and could not prevent the prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population until today. We conclude that the narrow focus of land-use policies on land sparing falls short in effectively balancing societal needs and ecosystem functions.

1. Introduction

Land-use competition constitutes one of the fundamental trade-offs between environment and development policies in the Global South (Mertz and Mertens, 2017). Rising demand for land-based resources by domestic and foreign investors for commercial agriculture, mining and forest conservation increases pressure on land and traditional land users (Brogaard et al., 2017b; Haberl et al., 2014). Land-use policies have to navigate trade-offs between competing interests across temporal and spatial scales, considering, for example, the agricultural land needed to ensure food security while conserving land for carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation (Messerli et al., 2015a).

Research distinguishes two possible directions in dealing with land-use competition: land sparing and land sharing (Mertz and Mertens, 2017). Land sparing assumes that clearly separated intensive agriculture

and forest conservation are best suited for reconciling development and environmental goals (Gibson et al., 2011; Phalan et al., 2011). The Borlaug hypothesis, for example, specifies that improvements in agricultural technology and ensuing higher yields result in land being spared for nature (Phalan, 2018). Land sharing, on the other hand, claims environmental and agricultural benefits from mosaic landscapes are more likely to preserve biodiversity in the long term, integrating low-intensity agriculture and managed forests along a continuum from field to fallow to forest (Perfecto and Vandermeer, 2010; Rerkasem et al., 2009a). While the scientific debate acknowledges the context-specific benefits and drawbacks of both approaches (Fischer et al., 2014; Law and Wilson, 2015; Meli et al., 2019; Phalan, 2018), in practice, policies often prioritize land sparing as a preferred alternative (Castella et al., 2013; Mertz and Mertens, 2017; Padoch and Sunderland, 2013). Often, this is formalized in national programs for Reduced

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Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation (REDD+) under the aegis of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

In Lao PDR (Laos), these divergent paradigms coexist, while proponents of each struggle for legitimacy as discourses crystallize into policies and practices under REDD+ and green economy directives (Pichler and Ingalls, 2021). At the crux of this issue lies the precarious present and uncertain future of traditional land-sharing shifting cultivation systems and largely state-driven initiatives to promote land sparing through agricultural intensification and enhanced forest conservation, a putatively more rational use of land (GoL, 2005; Ingalls et al., 2018). Laos aims at improving livelihoods, reducing poverty and graduating from its least developed status by the year 2024 (Souksavanh and Lipes, 2018), largely by tapping its terrestrial resources. Forests feature prominently in both socio-economic development and environmental protection programs with the overarching goal of reaching 70% forest cover (Phimmavong et al., 2009). The dual focus of the land sparing paradigm on forest protection and socio-economic development is especially appealing to a country like Laos with high levels of poverty and a self-declared dependence on the exploitation of natural resources for economic development (GoL, 2005; Lestrelin et al., 2012; Vongvisouk et al., 2016).

While land sparing synergies are framed explicitly in Lao land-use policies, inherent trade-offs remain largely implicit. Nevertheless, numerous studies have analyzed such trade-offs regarding biodiversity (see Mertz and Mertens (2017) for an overview) or challenged the basic assumption that intensified agriculture leads to spared land and might instead lead to an expansion of agricultural land (Ceddia et al., 2014; Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011; Rudel et al., 2009), a phenomenon more generally described as Jevon's paradox (Phalan, 2018). Research increasingly addresses synergies and trade-offs with regard to carbon sequestration, as land sparing in theory leads to reforestation, considered one of the most important nature-based solutions for climate change (Hertel, 2012; Griscom et al., 2017). A number of studies compare carbon sequestration in spared forests and intensified cropland (e.g. Bruun et al., 2009; Gilroy et al., 2014; Lamb et al., 2016; Williams et al., 2018), and highlight greenhouse gas emissions associated with land-use intensification and agricultural industrialization such as the increased direct or indirect (e.g. in fertilizers) use of fossil fuels (e.g. Burney et al., 2010; Gingrich et al., 2019; Lamb et al., 2016).

Land sparing is also seen as an environmentally sound solution to meet rising food demand (Phalan et al., 2011), entailing land-use intensification and often commercialization, a process that often affects poor people's access to local food systems as forests, fallows, and agricultural fields are converted into more intensive agriculture (Broegaard et al., 2017a). This land-use change raises concerns about food security and resilience to price fluctuations, among others, as farmers abandon food crop production in favor of cash crops (Castella et al., 2013; Thanichanon et al., 2018).

Employing a social-ecological lens, this paper investigates land sparing strategies of Laos in terms of their environmental and socio-economic impacts in the period from 2000 to 2019. To this end, we (1) examine the discursive dimension of sparing land and reducing shifting cultivation in policy documents, identifying and characterizing major narratives; and (2) analyze biophysical processes associated with land sparing, focusing on (2a) land-use change, (2b) ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions, and (2c) agricultural intensification and food security.

2. Methods

2.1. Discursive analysis of policy documents

The government of Laos (GoL) has identified the stabilization and reduction of shifting cultivation as a major political goal. It is formulated, for example, in the Lao Forestry Strategy to the Year 2020 (GoL,

2005), the National Socio-Economic Development Plans (NSEDPs) (GoL, 2016, 2006), the National Growth and Poverty Eradication Strategy (GoL, 2004) and is advanced as a cornerstone in Laos' Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to climate change mitigation (GoL, 2015) and REDD+ documents (GoL, 2018, 2010). The Forestry Strategy explicitly summarizes Lao land-use policies since the 1980s and describes, among others, the environmental arguments in favor of reducing shifting cultivation. The National Socio-Economic Development Plans (NSEDPs) represent Lao economic development policies and highlight the economic benefits in terms of poverty reduction and food security associated with land sparing.

To analyze the discursive dimension of land sparing, we build on Mayring (2014) and conduct a qualitative content analysis focusing particularly on the Forestry Strategy 2020 (GoL, 2005) and the 6th and 8th NSEDPs (GoL, 2016, 2006), which are available online and in English. We use the coding software Atlas.ti to systemize and code targets, arguments and planned measures associated with reducing shifting cultivation in the three strategy papers. We choose the 6th and the 8th NSEDPs covering the years 2006–2010 and 2016–2020 in order to cover the timespan comprised by the Forestry Strategy as well as to detect changes in focus and rationale. Additionally, we qualitatively review Laos' REDD+ Readiness Preparation Plan of 2010 (GoL, 2010), first INDC report (GoL, 2015) and Reference Emissions-level report (DoF, 2018) in which the Lao government legitimizes the reduction of shifting cultivation in the context of carbon sequestration.

2.2. Biophysical assessment of land-use change

We use biophysical evidence to quantify changes in shifting cultivation in Laos since 2000 as well as specific ecological and economic impacts associated to land-use change.

2.2.1. Land-use change

To study changes in area extent and discuss land-use competition between conservation and production, we use national-level land-use change matrices between 2000 and 2019, focusing on changes in agricultural and forest lands: a decrease of shifting cultivation area would represent land-use segregation, i.e., a successful implementation of land sparing strategies. Data are provided online by the Lao Department of Forestry (DoF) and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) for the periods 2000–2005, 2005–2010, 2010–2015, and 2015–2019 (<https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>).

Typically, land-cover assessments cannot detect the dynamic land-use system of shifting cultivation and no exact figures of one shifting cultivation land-cover category appear in land-use statistics (Heinimann et al., 2013). The classification used by the DoF allows distinguishing shifting cultivation area from forest and agricultural land, with "regenerating vegetation" and "upland crops" as the two land types considered to be mainly fallows and shifting cultivation plots. "Rice paddies", "agricultural plantations" and "other agricultural land" represent more intensively used, permanent agriculture, and "current forest" (in contrast to regenerating forest) is disaggregated into six ecological categories.

We use these data from national sources in our analyses because national decision makers use those data for land management plans and political strategies. However, we compare the national data to data compilations by FAOstat, providing much less information on shifting cultivation, but covering a longer time period (since 1990) and using a different forest definition. FAOstat data include forest areas with more than 10% canopy cover on 0.5 ha, while national data only report areas with more than 20% canopy cover on 0.5 ha as forests (DoF, 2018; FAO, 2012). Therefore, differences in values indirectly inform about forest quality. The land-use change matrices based on national data not only inform on a more detailed level about land-use changes, but are also the basis for accounting ecosystem carbon sequestration.

2.2.2. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions

Changes in ecosystem carbon stocks and agricultural emissions are analyzed as proxies of climate impacts of land-use change in Laos in the period 2000–2019. We assess carbon stock changes in ecosystem biomass (excluding soil) through a stock-difference approach (IPCC, 2019, 2006) of six different forest categories, three agricultural land categories and two categories comprising shifting cultivation land. Carbon density values for 15 different land-cover categories are derived from DoF and IPCC (DoF, 2020, 2018; DoF and JICA, 2017; IPCC, 2003).

As we apply one value of carbon density for each land-use category, we can identify carbon fluxes due to conversion within forests, for example, from evergreen forests to plantations, or from evergreen forests to upland crops. We cannot, however, segregate different successional stages of shifting cultivation fallows, as we are not differentiating between young growth and old growth or between different ecological zones within Laos. Over- or underestimation of the carbon stored within this land-use category is likely, as is the overestimation of carbon stored in other forest categories where we cannot account for varying degrees of degradation (Gibbs et al., 2007; Hett et al., 2011). Bruun et al. (2018) and McNicol et al. (2015) have shown in Lao case studies that carbon stocks of fallows are systematically underestimated as the complex dynamics of root biomass and soil organic carbon in fallows remain poorly understood. In order to enable a better approximation of shifting cultivation-based carbon fluxes we compare respective national carbon stock values of regenerating vegetation with minimum and maximum values reported in the literature (Ziegler et al., 2012).

We complement the carbon stock-change estimation with an analysis of emissions from agricultural activities based on data provided by FAOstat (www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GT), computed at Tier 1 following the IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories (IPCC, 2006, 2002, 2000, 1997, 1996). Results indicate to which extent emissions from land-use intensification compromise the forest carbon sink enabled by land-use segregation (Burney et al., 2010). Due to lack of data, our analysis is limited by i) excluding additional emissions from fossil-fuel based inputs (e.g. fertilizers, tractors) and from soils, ii) not discerning agricultural emissions intrinsic to different agricultural systems, and iii) not quantifying emissions per ton of (food and non-food) products of different cultivation systems.

2.2.3. Agricultural intensification and food security

To assess links between land-use change and food security in Laos, we use FAOstat to derive annual data on production, harvested area and trade of agricultural products, related to shifting cultivation (upland rice) and to commodified agriculture (maize, cassava, sugarcane, bananas, coffee) in the period 2000–2019 (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>). National statistics by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, available since 2009, are used to corroborate aggregated FAO data. These provide more disaggregated data than FAOstat on the production of rice, the most important crop in Laos (Manivong and Cramb, 2020), that indicate subsistence farming (lowland rainfed rice), shifting cultivation (upland rainfed rice), and more commercialized farming systems (lowland irrigated rice), addressing impacts of agricultural system changes on rice production. We use population data provided by FAOstat (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OA>).

Additionally, we analyze certain food security indicators. “Average dietary energy supply adequacy” operationalizes the physical availability of food which “addresses the ‘supply side’ of food security and is determined by the level of food production, stock levels and net trade” (FAO, 2008, p. 1). In addition, we investigate “prevalence of undernourishment” and “prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population” acknowledging that the mere supply of food does not guarantee household level food security. These indicators operationalize the physical access to food as presented as indicators for SDG target 2 “End Hunger” (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal2>). All food (in-) security indicators are derived from FAOstat (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS>). While this selection is limited and not

representative of the actual food security of certain groups or individuals in the country, it captures biophysical variables (as opposed to monetary variables) that are associated with food security in the analyzed policy documents, and therefore allows for a review of the assumed relation between land sparing and food security.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental and socio-economic narratives to legitimize the reduction of shifting cultivation

Since the late 1980s, reducing shifting cultivation is a common goal in policies targeting socio-economic development and environmental protection in Laos (Castella et al., 2013; GoL, 2006, pp. 13; 176, 2005, pp. 39; 58). Based on the policy documents analyzed, we identified two narratives legitimizing this goal in the last 20 years (see Fig. 1): a socio-economic and an environmental narrative. Land sparing features prominently in both narratives, but is argued in different ways.

3.1.1. Socio-economic narrative: Reduction of shifting cultivation enhances food security and exports

The socio-economic narrative is based on the prevalent assumption that shifting cultivation is an “out-dated” (GoL, 2006, p. 176) form of agriculture. Therefore, “the areas of slash-and-burn rice cultivation should be reduced by introducing new livelihood alternatives, such as industrial tree plantations and commercial crops, livestock rearing, and other permanent livelihood alternatives” (GoL, 2006, p. 135). The Lao government prioritizes intensive, permanent and commercialized agriculture and forestry over shifting cultivation:

“The Government has concentrated on the development of agricultural production, to reorient the agriculture sector from semi-subsistence and subsistence to commercial production to ensure the enhanced supply of raw materials to the processing industries, meeting the growing domestic requirements for agricultural products, and rapidly expanding agricultural exports.” (GoL, 2006, p. 1).

Supply of fertilizers, pesticides, and improved, high yielding plant and livestock varieties, as well as implementation of irrigation systems and better infrastructure aims at upgrading farming methods (GoL, 2016, 2006). Concomitant yield increases as well as improved market access shall on the one hand improve people’s living standards, especially of subsistence farmers, by generating income, enhancing farmers’ job stability (GoL, 2016, p. 145), and leading to “firm food security” (GoL, 2006, p. 13). Especially the upgrading of rice production for domestic consumption and for reserves is expected to improve food security (GoL, 2016, p. 57, 2006, p. 135). On the other hand, cash crops like “corn, tobacco, coffee, beans, rubber, cassava, sugar cane, vegetables, and many types of fruit” (GoL, 2006, p. 65), high value trees (GoL, 2016, p. 107) and livestock (buffaloes, cattle) (GoL, 2016, p. 99) are promoted as export commodities. Increases of both domestic supply or food security improvements and export volumes imply an intensification of agriculture and the reduction of shifting cultivation.

Altogether, the “reorientation from shifting cultivation” to an intensified, commercialized agriculture should “gradually uplift the quality of life of the affected populations” (GoL, 2006, p. 34) and “reduce poverty among the ethnic people” (GoL, 2010, p. 10, 2006, p. 19).

3.1.2. Environmental narrative: Reduction of shifting cultivation supports forest conservation

Within the environmental narrative, shifting cultivation is framed as one of the main causes of deforestation and especially forest degradation (GoL, 2010, p. 30, 2005, p. 13), as “threats to forest and environment” (GoL, 2005, p. 42) and “one of the main causes of forest loss” (GoL, 2005, p. 42). “Alarming” rates of deforestation and forest degradation (GoL, 2005, p. 2) reinforce the goal to rehabilitate, preserve and expand forests to 70% of Laos’ total territory (GoL, 2005, p. 3). As one of the

Fig. 1. Narratives on socio-economic and environmental implications of land sparing or reducing shifting cultivation, derived from a qualitative analysis of policy documents in Laos.

main obstacles to increase forest cover, shifting cultivation shall thus be substituted by “rationalize[d] forest use” (GoL, 2005, p. 4). Large scale and industrial actors are acknowledged next to subsistence farmers as main drivers of deforestation and forest degradation (GoL, 2010). Derived measures, however, are mainly directed towards reducing shifting cultivation or illegal logging because they are “more directly under the control of the forest authorities” (GoL, 2018, 2010, p. 9; Skutsch and Turnhout, 2020).

The classification of different forest types as production, protection, conservation, regeneration and degraded forest (GoL, 2005, p. 11) supports the segregation between intensely and economically used forest areas on the one hand and spared, environmentally protected forest areas on the other hand. This stands in contrast to the shared land use of alternating shifting cultivation plots. Shifting cultivation fallows are classified as “degraded forest”, as “forests that have been heavily damaged, [...] that are classified for tree planting and/or allocation to individuals or organizations for tree planting, permanent agriculture and livestock production or other purposes in accordance with national economic development plans” (GoL, 2005, p. 11). The Forestry Strategy emphasizes that the categories of degraded and regeneration forest “make explicit intentions to regenerate natural forest by stabilizing

shifting cultivation and to productively utilize degraded forest land” (GoL, 2005, p. 11).

The environmental aims of forest conservation and reforestation shifted over the time period: Biodiversity conservation and stable wood supply have been prominent reasonings in the Forestry Strategy and the 6th NSEDP (GoL, 2006, p. 136, 2005, pp. 31; 51). Carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation in the context of international programs such as REDD+ became more important in recent years (GoL, 2016, p. 142, 2010, p. 48).

3.2. Land-use change, emissions and agricultural intensification

The identified narratives are based on the explicit or implicit assumptions that land-use intensification enables forest regrowth and increases ecosystem carbon sequestration, while increasing food security.

3.2.1. Land-use change

Since 2000, Lao forest area decreased according to both national and international data sources, albeit at different levels. National data show decreasing forest cover from 61% of the total land area in 2000 to 58% in 2019 (Fig. 2a), whereas FAO data (Fig. 2b) show decreasing forest

Fig. 2. Land-use change in Laos. National data present land-use change between 2000 and 2019 (a); Source: <https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>; FAO data present land-use change between 1990 and 2019 (b); Source: FAOstat.

cover from 71% in 2000 to 68% in 2019. The discrepancy in forest extent is due to different forest definitions in the two data sources. The difference in forest area might represent shifting cultivation fallow areas in early succession stages with canopy covers between 10% and 20%: the national dataset (Fig. 3a-d) shows that more upland crop plots are converted into regenerating vegetation (0.19/0.21/0.20/0.10 Mha/yr in 2000–2005/2005–2010/2010–2015/2015–2019) than the other way around (0.15/0.18/0.09/0.09 Mha/yr in the same periods), indicating aging fallows and a net abandonment or intensification of active shifting cultivation plots. Also, the FAOstat category “other land” is stagnating (16% in 2000, 17% in 2019). “Other land” is classifiable neither as forest nor as agricultural land, and thus can – like shifting cultivation areas – be both at the same time. Fallow areas seem to reach the threshold of 10% canopy cover, but not 20%, therefore those fallows are categorized as forests in the FAO data, and stagnate as “regenerating vegetation” in the national data (Fig. 2a, b). Due to the more inclusive forest definition in FAOstat, land-use changes or ecological succession processes are detected in this dataset rather quickly, but there is a risk of misinterpretations, e.g. of long-term fallows as “regenerated forest”. The DoF definition of “forest land” on the other hand has been adapted explicitly to avoid such misinterpretations by considering the typically

quick ecological succession in tropical and subtropical areas so that e.g. shifting cultivation fallows are not mistakenly classified as (sparse) forest (DoF, 2018). Still, the differentiation between “regenerating vegetation” and “mixed deciduous forest” remains challenging and possibly leads to an underestimation of the area extent of older fallows.

Both datasets show cropland expansions from 8% to 10% (FAO) and from 7 to 11% (national data) of total land between 2000 and 2019. Fig. 3a-c show that conversions into cropland (rice paddies and other agriculture (RP & OA)) mainly originate from former forests or regenerating vegetation. Conversions from forestland to upland crops do not occupy a large area, but were increasing from 2005 to 2015 (Fig. 3b-c), indicating that upland farmers still practiced pioneering shifting cultivation but at a small area extent. In the latest period from 2015 to 2019 (Fig. 3d), the share of forestland converted into upland crops decreased again, indicating a stabilization of pioneering shifting cultivation.

Our results thus show a slight decrease and then stabilization of shifting cultivation area with presumably increasing canopy density, while (primary) forests keep decreasing. Cropland expanded into both these land-use categories.

Fig. 3. Land conversions in the time periods 2000–2005 (a), 2005–2010 (b), 2010–2015 (c), and 2015–2019 (d). “RP & OA” stands for “Rice paddies and other agriculture”. Underlying data: <https://nfms.maf.gov.la/>, own representation.

3.2.2. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions

Our assessment of ecosystem carbon stock changes reveals that land-use changes reduced ecosystem carbon stocks and caused net GHG emissions. GHG emissions increased from about 11 Mt CO₂-equivalents per year during 2000–2005 to about 15 Mt CO₂-equivalents per year from 2015 to 2019 (Fig. 4a). Analyzing the GHG effects of land-use changes in forests, agricultural land and shifting cultivation area, we see that the main emitting process was the conversion of forestland into shifting cultivation area, contributing 70% (2000–2005), 52% (2005–2010), 74% (2010–2015), and 62% (2015–2019) to gross land-use change related emissions (Fig. 4a). Conversions of forestland and shifting cultivation area into cropland also constitute emitting processes. Gross emissions of forestland to cropland conversions increased from 17% in 2000–2005 to 20% in 2015–2019. Gross emissions of conversions from shifting cultivation to cropland on the other hand decreased from 12% in 2000–2005 to 1% in 2015–2019, partly because such conversions occurred less, and partly because less fallows and more upland crop plots with reduced carbon stocks were converted. Converging carbon stocks in shifting cultivation areas and cropland result in less emissions in cases of conversion between those categories (DoF, 2020). Remaining land-use change related emissions were caused by conversions from forests to other land, and by conversions within forests.

GHG removals, i.e. carbon sinks, occurred mainly due to conversion of shifting cultivation area into forestland (54% of gross removals in 2000–2005, 83% in 2005–2015, and 87% in 2015–2019). Other land conversions additionally contributed to carbon sequestration at lesser extent, e.g. conversions within forests in 2000–2005, between shifting cultivation categories, or conversions from cropland to shifting cultivation area.

The magnitude of GHG emitting or removing processes depends on both the area extent and the respective carbon density values. Therefore, our results are sensitive to uncertainties in carbon density values. For the most contested carbon density value of regenerating vegetation, the DoF allocates rather low values (13.6 tC/ha) compared to the minimum (3 tC/ha) and maximum (138 tC/ha) values found in the literature (Ziegler et al., 2012), assuming short fallows (<7 years) and long fallows (>10 years), respectively. Allocating a carbon density value to regenerating vegetation at the lower spectrum of values from the literature seems appropriate considering that i) DoF only allocates fallows of max. 7

years to “regenerating vegetation” (older fallows are considered “mixed deciduous forest”), and ii) after a conversion from any other land use, fallows can be max. 4 years old: 1–2 year(s) active plot followed by 3–4 years fallow during the observed 5-year periods.

The low level of detail of our database does not allow to distinguish between old and young fallows, which is why we refer to the (young fallow) DoF values, risking potentially great underestimation of carbon stocks in (old growth) regenerating vegetation (Bruun et al., 2018; Chan et al., 2016).

Agricultural emissions represent 28–38% of the gross emissions from land conversion and agricultural activities (Fig. 4a). They increased between 2000 and 2019 from around 7 Mt CO₂-equivalents/yr to ca. 10 Mt CO₂-equivalents/yr, mainly due to livestock related emissions like enteric fermentation (52% increase) and emissions from manure management and applications (89% increase) (Fig. 4b).

While the conversion of forestland into shifting cultivation area was the main emitting process in 2010–2015 (54% of gross land conversion and agricultural activity emissions), the expansion and intensification of agriculture caused emissions of a similar extent, and in 2000–2005, 2005–2010, and 2015–2019, the conversion of shifting cultivation area and forest into cropland plus the emissions from agricultural intensification caused more emissions than conversions into shifting cultivation (55% compared to 45%, 49% compared to 38%, and 46% compared to 43% respectively). Our results thus on the one hand confirm that a reduction of shifting cultivation results in carbon sequestration in forest biomass. On the other hand, however, they also highlight that the expansion of agricultural land and the shift towards intensive agriculture results in emissions of an equal or even higher order of magnitude.

3.2.3. Agricultural intensification and food security

The DoF dataset indicates that the area of permanent agriculture has expanded faster than shifting cultivation area has decreased, meaning that overall, forest cover has decreased. Disaggregated, the DoF data show increasing areas of rice paddies (1.16 Mha/yr in 2000 to 1.2 Mha/yr in 2015), “other agriculture” (0.41 Mha/yr in 2000 to 1.05 Mha/yr in 2015; together with rice paddies 2.38 Mha/yr in 2019), and agricultural plantations (0.05 Mha/yr in 2000 to 0.08 Mha/yr in 2019), while upland crop areas decreased (0.19 Mha/yr in 2000 to 0.13 Mha/yr in 2019) (Fig. 5a). “Other agriculture” is increasing so steeply that it

Fig. 4. Ecosystem carbon fluxes and agricultural emissions. a) Emissions and Removals of GHGs (in CO₂ equivalents/yr) due to land conversions and agricultural activities. F/F: conversions inside forests; SC/F: conversion from shifting cultivation (SC) to forest; C/F: conversion from cropland to forest; F/SC: conversion from forest to SC; SC/SC: conversion of SC fallows and active plots; C/CS: conversion from cropland to SC; F/C: conversion from forest to cropland; SC/C: conversion from SC to cropland. C/C: conversions within cropland. Net other land: conversions of all categories into other land and from other land into all categories. The bar charts indicate minimum and maximum net emissions based on min./max. values from the literature compared to emissions based on DoF C density values of SC. b) Agricultural Emissions in Mt CO₂ equivalents/yr in Laos; Source: FAOstat.

Fig. 5. Agricultural intensification displayed by cropland conversions and production quantities. a) Conversions within cropland 2000–2019 in Mha; Source: DoF; b) Crop production in Mt dry matter per year; source: FAOstat; disaggregated rice production in Mt dry matter / year; source: Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.

proportionally catches up with rice paddies in 2015, with maize, vegetables, cassava, and sugar cane as main contributors according to FAOstat. Rice, however, remains the most important crop regarding area and production output.

Crop production more than doubled between 2000 and 2019 from 2.3 Mt dry matter/yr to 5.2 Mt dry matter/yr with a peak in 2016 (6.6 Mt dry matter/yr), a much more rapid growth than that of the production area (1.6-fold), or that of population (1.3-fold) in the same period (Fig. 5b), indicating agricultural intensification and increasing per-capita production. “Cash crops” such as maize, cassava, sugar cane, and bananas contributed to the observed increase in production, partly due to expansion of cropland, partly due to increasing use of improved cultivars (Ingalls et al., 2018). Rice production also increased in absolute terms, but its share in total crop production declined from 82% in 2000 to 58% in 2019. Instead, the shares of maize, cassava and sugarcane increased from 4% to 13%, 1% to 12%, and 2% to 5% respectively between 2000 and 2019. Adverse weather conditions with severe floods and droughts as well as pest infestations led to steep declines in production quantities of rice (minus 15%) and maize (minus 49%) in 2018 and 2019 (FAO, 2020).

When looking at the more disaggregated national data on rice production, the category considered a shifting cultivation crop (“upland rainfed paddy”) decreased from c. 0.19 Mt dry matter/yr to 0.15 Mt dry matter/yr between 2009 and 2019, while the category considered a cash crop (“dry season paddy”) stagnated at around 0.4 Mt dry matter/yr (Fig. 5b). “Lowland rainfed paddy” however increased from around 2 Mt dry matter/yr in 2009 to c. 2.5 Mt/yr in 2019.

Laos is not a large importer or exporter of agricultural biomass, with gross trade flows accounting for less than 5% of agricultural production in the entire period since 2000. Nevertheless, trade experienced a steep rise since 2013 to up to 18% in 2017 due to increasing cassava (0.1 – 0.7 Mt of dry matter) and maize (0.10 – 0.16 Mt of dry matter) exports. Since 2008, Laos has been a net exporter of agricultural biomass products (Fig. 6a).

“Average dietary energy supply adequacy” exceeds 100% since 2004–2006, indicating a stable and sufficient national supply of nutritional energy (Fig. 6b). The prevalence of undernourishment decreased between 2000 and 2002 (31%) and between 2015 and 2017 (6%), and stagnated at a level of 5–6% until 2018–2020. No trend data of the prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population

Fig. 6. Agricultural trade and food security indicators. a) Physical trade balance of agricultural crops and livestock products; negative values indicate an export surplus, positive values indicate that more products are imported than exported; Source: FAOstat; b) Set of food security indicators: “Average dietary energy supply adequacy”, “Prevalence of undernourishment” and “Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population”; Source: FAOstat.

is available, only one value of 29.4% in 2018–2020, showing that there is still roughly one third of the population suffering of moderate or severe food insecurity today.

While the shift in relative contribution to agricultural production from upland crops to lowland rice and cash crops increased Lao export volume and availability of food, food insecurity still affects a high share of the Lao population.

4. Discussion

Our results provide empirical grounds for a more nuanced and critical reflection of the land sparing assumptions in Lao policies that legitimize the reduction of shifting cultivation: On the one hand, the stabilization of shifting cultivation resulted in recovery of some forest areas entailing gross carbon sequestration, while agricultural intensification improved dietary energy availability and increased agricultural exports. On the other hand, however, cropland expansion and intensification of agriculture resulted in equally high GHG emissions, and were unable to guarantee access to food for everyone.

The results confirm Vongvisouk et al.'s (2016) observation that land-use change in Laos resulted in “neither land sparing nor land sharing” (p. 190), as permanent croplands instead of forests substitute the slightly decreasing shifting cultivation area. No land was spared, and despite the establishment of National Protected Areas and the overarching aim to achieve 70% forest cover by 2020 (GoL, 2005), forest cover decreased between 2000 and 2019. At the same time, agricultural land use intensified *and* expanded as would be expected according to Jevons' paradox: efficiency increases due to agricultural intensification were overcompensated by the expansion of cropland that was much greater than that needed to replace the production from shifting cultivation, possibly due to rising demands and increasing margins (Phalan, 2018). Shifting cultivators who abandoned former plots and fallows partly did so because laws and policies restricted access and use of land to either agriculture or forestry and criminalized shifting cultivation, and partly because of improved integration into markets and infrastructure (Fujita and Phanvilay, 2008; Van Vliet et al., 2012). The transition from shifting cultivation to market-oriented, high yielding agriculture potentially results in immediate economic benefits for farmers, reducing their dependency on subsistence production (Evans et al., 2011; Van Vliet et al., 2012), though this may be more pronounced for wealthier farmers who possess sufficient resources for transition (Hepp et al., 2019). This, in addition to the policies promoting agricultural commercialization and intensification, possibly encouraged farmers and investors to transform and expand their agricultural production, leaving no land to be spared for conservation (Rudel et al., 2009; Van Vliet et al., 2013, 2012).

A positive contribution to climate change mitigation through land sparing can only succeed if the reduction of shifting cultivation is met with forest protection and increased carbon sequestration (Burney et al., 2010). We found that conversions from forestland to shifting cultivation areas caused the highest land-use change related GHG emissions. Soil organic carbon of shifting cultivation plots, however, was not considered. According to recent and Lao-specific studies by Bruun et al. (2021) and McNicol et al. (2015), shifting cultivation fallows store much more carbon in soil and root biomass than is typically expected. Taking soil organic carbon and root biomass in fallows into account could therefore change the picture.

The actual extent of land-use change induced carbon emissions and removals can only be approximated, because biomass carbon densities in shifting cultivation systems are highly context-specific and data availability is poor. Biomass carbon density depends, among others, on the length of the fallows in shifting systems, and on forest characteristics (primary or planted forest, species of planted trees, etc.) (Fox et al., 2014). Hence, future benefits of promoted land-use changes (e.g. shifting cultivation to segregated agriculture/forest) in terms of carbon removals might be limited. The promotion of one unspecified land-use category against another with presumably less carbon sequestration

potential might be disproportionate, as the specifics of those categories can change the whole picture (Mertz et al., 2021) – long-fallow shifting systems for example may store as much carbon as intact forests, while short-fallow systems (Ziegler et al., 2012) may store less carbon than perennial plantations of e.g. rubber (Bruun et al., 2018), whereas systems of permanent cropping of continuous annual field crops (Ziegler et al., 2012) might store less carbon than even intensive shifting cultivation systems (Bruun et al., 2021).

In addition to the low carbon sequestration potential of permanent cropland, agricultural intensification itself is a source of growing GHG emissions that may compromise protected forest carbon sinks (Gingrich et al., 2019). Our results show that emissions related to intensive livestock farming and rice cultivation aggregate and, together with the emissions of land conversions into cropland, can reach the level of emissions produced by land conversions from forests into shifting cultivation area. The high GHG emissions from permanent agriculture (e.g. emissions from fertilizer production) as well as emissions associated to shorter fallow periods (e.g. emissions from soil degradation) are so far missing in narratives supporting the reduction of shifting cultivation and should be integrated in future policies for the benefit of more expedient land-based climate change mitigation measures (Scheidel, 2018).

While our results show that agricultural outputs increased in total, per hectare, and per capita, thus contributing to an improvement in the average national availability of food and a decrease of biomass import dependency, FAO data suggest that food security is still precarious. Undernourishment and moderate to severe food insecurity prevail until today at considerable levels. Land sparing policies assume that the mosaic landscapes of shifting cultivation are “underutilized” (Messerli et al., 2015b; Scheidel and Work, 2018) and neglect empirical evidence that small-scale agriculture adopting agroecological methods can be as productive as industrial agriculture, or even more productive (Perfecto and Vandermeer, 2010). This perception may have negative implications for climate change mitigation (if plantations or cropland with low carbon density substitute long-fallows) but also questions customary land use and ultimately endangers local people's food security (Keovilignavong and Suhardiman, 2020). Further, there is a large degree of uncertainty regarding the adequacy of food security indicators with respect to their ability to capture the overall diversity of plant and animal species used within complex systems (Armstrong, 2018; Barrett, 2010; Jones et al., 2013). Typically, comparative analyses of agricultural production between extensive (i.e. those based on land sharing) and intensive agricultural production systems, and their relationship to food security, include only the formal or dominant agricultural product. In rotational agriculture systems in Lao PDR and similar contexts this is typically rice. Artificially narrowing comparative analyses in this way excludes one of the key features of extensive upland systems, wherein ancillary crops and species — particularly non-timber forest products (NTFPs) — play a crucial role in overall production at the landscape level. While no national-level assessment of production and consumption levels of these species has been carried out, a growing body of literature sheds some light on this particular matter (e.g. Bouapao et al., 2016; Epprecht et al., 2018; Hett et al., 2012; Ingalls and Dwyer, 2016; Keovilignavong and Suhardiman, 2020; Renard and Tilman, 2019). NTFPs collected from shifting cultivation fields and their associated fallows in many areas comprise the principal source of the non-rice diet and, in some cases, exceed the value of rice sales in their proportional contribution to the household income (Ingalls and Roth, 2018). While land sparing advocates imply that forest conservation necessarily leads to overall increase in NTFPs (because of the supposed positive association between these and forests — the F in NTFP), this does not appear to be the case. Emergent data from a 10-year assessment of more than 3000 upland households in Lao PDR indicates rather that 48% of NTFP sale values derive from shifting cultivation fields and their fallows, versus only 10% from mature forest areas (Ingalls and Roth, 2018). Intensive agricultural systems, which are explicitly designed and managed to limit

species diversity within cropping regimes, are comparatively lacking in these values (Rerkasem et al., 2009b). The prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity is likely linked to the expansion of commercial agriculture that often leads to the specialization in a small number of cash crops (Thanichanon et al., 2018). This specialization leaves farmers vulnerable to extreme weather events and food price volatility and, at times, limits their ability to buy food (FAO, 2020; Thanichanon et al., 2018). Additionally, increasing the share of intensively produced food might (further) skew internal inequalities in food distribution. The commercialization of agriculture enhanced the well-being of many well-connected villages but it also exacerbated the threat of food insecurity for certain groups of the population less connected to distant markets (Castella and Phaipasith, 2021; Nanthavong et al., 2021). While shifting cultivation used to be a reliable food security practice for most, land degradation due to shortened fallows has led to poor harvests and an unstable food supply (Ramcilovic-Suominen and Kotilainen, 2020), as well as the degradation of underlying soils (Mertz et al., 2009; Vandergeest, 2003) and the robustness of fallow-based resources (Fox et al., 2014; Fujita and Phanvilay, 2008). Therefore, further marginalizing shifting cultivation has direct negative implications for food security of the most vulnerable rural populations in Lao PDR, by depriving them from the collection of NFTP which are a crucial additional source of food or income (Jendresen and Rasmussen, 2022; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Kotilainen, 2020; Vongvisouk et al., 2014). This deprivation has not been compensated by agricultural intensification on permanent croplands.

5. Concluding remarks

Our analysis combined qualitative and quantitative approaches to study the discursive and biophysical dimensions of land sparing strategies in Laos, focusing on a reduction of shifting cultivation. We highlight that while the reduction of shifting cultivation is politically considered a win-win solution to achieve economic and environmental aims, the biophysical trends in land-use change, GHG emissions and food security only partially support this perception because the shift to intensive commercial agriculture also negatively affects GHG emissions and was unable to eradicate food insecurity even in years with high production. Effective land-use policies need nuanced perspectives, addressing positive and negative implications of all agricultural and forest practices.

This begs the question of the degree to which interventions designed to avoid forest carbon emissions and enhance atmospheric carbon removals are able to produce these outcomes in practice. Our research suggests that where such interventions focus on land sparing approaches that transform (some part of) shifting cultivation systems to intensive agriculture, these outcomes are ambiguous at best. Beyond all this, the particular promise of REDD+ — to take one example of a global policy initiative wherein the carbon implications of competing land uses are explicitly addressed — is that it is intended as a tool not only to address forest carbon emissions (and thus climate change mitigation), but also to achieve ancillary positive outcomes for biodiversity and people. Insofar as REDD+ approaches and land-use policies in general are grounded in and share the assumptions of land sparing paradigms, we suggest that they will largely fail to achieve these. Creating political space for land sharing and carbon-cycle management through extensive systems, while also explicitly recognizing potential tradeoffs, may yet achieve a more realistic, negotiated ‘win-win’ for a more sustainable future.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106293.

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